

Implementation of System Information Analysis

Raihan Thabit Ananda Kusuma, Department of Industrial Engineering, Faculty of Engineering,
Andalas University, Padang, West Sumatra, Indonesia

Abstract—A system within an organization that meets the needs of daily transaction management, supports operations, is managerial, strategic activities from providing certain outside parties with reports and an organization and is needed. There are some implementation that we mainstreamly found in the industry, such as an E-Commerce in small business, warehousing, and tourism. Micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) in Indonesia today is one of the backbones of a resilient economy to the shocks of the economic crisis. MSMEs in Indonesia growing in tandem with the development of a typical business area. The advantages that the company gets by having implementation of warehousing management, namely: avoiding expenses that are not important in a company, with warehousing management can improve business development and regulation in a company, anticipate the occurrence of data manipulation and errors in input data, especially human error. At the stage of implementing the information system marketing of the island tourism product which has been designed to be able to be used by fishermen in marketing their services island tour transportation. Big Dipper fisherman is given training on the use of marketing information systems marketing Island tourism to increase the number of tourists as an effort to increase the economy of Big Dipper fishermen. So, implementation of information systems could make large change to modernize the traditional ways.

Index Terms—Implementation, Warehousing, E-Commerce, Tourism, Information Systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

Development of science information and communication technology that very quickly open up opportunities for the business people to increase their income and expand the reach of the industrial sector. This development accelerated so rapidly after emergence of the internet. Internet provides a new method for business people to innovate for the advancement of their company.

For example, In industry warehousing management is needed to control warehousing activities. With this control, it is expected to reduce unnecessary costs for warehousing needs, incoming goods and outgoing goods from the warehouse must be correct and in accordance with demand, the accuracy of the inventory in the warehouse. In other cases, development is also needed to expand the interaction between managers and consumers. The implementation of information system analysis can also be developed for the tourism industry to reach tourists who want to come or just looking for information about the destinations to be visited.

The effectiveness and efficiency of information systems is a key aspect that can determine the progress or decline of an organization. Manufacturing industry can not be separated from this. An effective and properly implemented information system will affect the management's performance in controlling the production system of the manufacturing industry. However, an information system that is too complex and complicated can reduce the efficiency of the overall production system.[1]

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A system within an organization that meets the needs of daily transaction management, supports operations, is managerial, strategic activities from providing certain outside parties with reports and an organization and is needed.[2]

Information system, an integrated set of components for collecting, storing, and processing data and for providing information, knowledge, and digital products. Business firms and other organizations rely on information systems to carry out and manage their operations, interact with their customers and suppliers, and compete in the marketplace. Information systems are used to run interorganizational supply chains and electronic markets. For instance, corporations use information systems to process financial accounts, to manage their human resources, and to reach their potential customers with online promotions. Many major companies are built entirely around information systems. The main components of information systems are computer hardware and software, telecommunications, databases and data warehouses, human resources, and procedures. The hardware, software, and telecommunications constitute information technology (IT), which is now ingrained in the operations and management of organizations.

An information system is the result of human design and consists of various components within an organization to achieve a goal, namely providing information which is useful. Information systems are one aspect of required by the organization. Forward or backward a organization is represented by the effectiveness and efficiency of the system information used by the organization Leman. General information system objectives include, provide information that can assist the process management decision making; Simplify carrying out daily operations; and Providing information appropriate for parties outside the organization, especially regarding issues management transparency. Information systems must be able to support business strategy company. The business strategy is realized through a series of business

processes, so that the ideal business process is the foundation for the development of information systems. The business process describes all the activities carried out in a system. Inputs, processes, outputs, actors involved, the flow of data and information can be identified through business process description

There are some implementation that we mainstreamly found in the industry, such as an E-Commerce in small business, warehousing, and tourism.

III. DISCUSSION

In this subchapter we will discuss the implementation of information systems analysis for some of the cases previously mentioned, such as an E-Commerce in small business, warehousing, and tourism.

A. E-Commerce in small business

Micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) in Indonesia today is one of the backbones of a resilient economy to the shocks of the economic crisis. MSMEs in Indonesia growing in tandem with the development of a typical business area. Businesses related to regional conditions too related to the geographical conditions of Bangka Island and the Belitung which uses a lot of marine products. This to improve that MSMEs are good job provider quite significant. Typical regional business in the Bangka Islands Belitung in general is processing marine products into fish snacks, traditional medicine, and accessories. aside from that There are several other types of small and medium businesses. MSMEs are difficult to develop significantly due to the limited marketing area. One way to gain market share MSME products can be wider is by changing the way and sales strategy. Therefore, this research aims to analyze the factors that encourage or hindering MSME business actors in the Bangka Islands Belitung by utilizing electronic commerce or e-commerce.

Based on several research results that have been carried out, it can be drawn the conclusion that currently there are many SMEs in Indonesia various areas that have utilized information technology to market their products. Information technology that has utilized by MSMEs varies from just using email, social media, websites, or a combination all three. Some of these studies also describe several advantages of using information technology, such as: facilitate work, facilitate promotion, and expand the market.

Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) is a method that changes the way humans take the decision from originally using the word to be using numbers. AHP can be widely used by business people to evaluate their business strategies that relating to customer service, geographic area, using business support technology, and the magnitude advantage AHP can also be implemented for evaluate the impact of E-Commerce websites for promote tourism business in Vietnam. Success online transactions in the E-Commerce business depends on mechanism for recommending products that can be done by utilizing trust and social relations. Often AHP is used in several studies because AHP can be a method of decision making in groups with reliable results . A new approach to decision

making with AHP developed to proportionally increase adaptation balanced scale Implementation of AHP as a method decision making in groups to evaluate performance of E-Commerce enterprises in theory [3].

The results of this study are presented in graphical form shows the ranking of the selected criteria and alternatives. The rating criteria will also be equipped with the amount of weight in percentages that make it clear how much an achievement is criteria after the data is obtained and combined with the device Expert Choice software. As for the alternative ranking is the final result that appears and becomes the basis for taking decision. The results of the study can be seen as a whole in the analytic hierarchical structure, or can also be viewed per criteria complete with alternatives. Full presentation and partial for each criterion can provide complete information for decision makers. Decision makers can be more pay close attention to what criteria and sub-criteria are most influential in efforts to encourage success MSMEs use information technology.[3]

B. Warehousing

Warehousing Management at CV. ABB hasn't been so good like warehouse data collection, part request data, spare part stock data, data expenditure of spare parts, and data on purchase orders that are still very manual. Currently at CV. ABB doesn't have any tools yet supervision of the use of spare parts and for data collection of spare parts parts are only handwritten by employees, so they are very vulnerable the occurrence of an employee error who recorded and possibility of data manipulation. Frequent loss of spares parts in the warehouse, fake receipts, and no tools yet supervision to supervise spare parts in the warehouse. PHP and MySQL are open source tools in development of a web-based information system that can used to solve this problem. System This web-based information will help make it easier spare part supervision because it is cheap and relatively easy to used without having to install from the client side. In overcome existing problems need to be repaired warehousing management so that the existing warehouse management in CV. ABB can be better, accountable and transparent. [4]

The advantages that the company gets by having implementation of warehousing management, namely: avoiding expenses that are not important in a company, with warehousing management can improve business development and regulation in a company, anticipate the occurrence of data manipulation and errors in input data, especially human error.

One of components is data dictionary. data dictionary is a collection of data and fact information of an information system in accordance with the needs. Data dictionary stores usernames, types of access allowed, the data item and the name of the data item in the database for perform the inspection. While data dictionary can store the size and type of data items, data item constraints, and the name of the item in the data integrity check. Data Dictionary consists of various kinds, namely: alias or pseudonym, the name of the data flow that flows in the DFD, the current data from or to the process, the explanation used to explain the existing information, the form of the data whether in the form of files, print outs or reports, data structures For example, current data consists of anything that is stored in the data dictionary, period and volume.[4]

Database design is a process that produces a detailed data model of the database, database design involves selecting: columns for each table and how tables and columns interact with each other [9]. Term database design can function as an application of the whole design process, not just the structure

database, but also queries and forms that have functions as part of the overall database within a database management system. The steps of database design are:[4]

1. Determine the purpose of the database.
2. Collect and search all the required information, e.g. order number and product name.
3. Divide the data that has been obtained into a table, then for any information in the subject or major entity.
4. Turn each piece of information into a column and decide name information that should be stored in the table.
5. Determine the primary key, select the primary key for each table.
6. Arrange the relations between tables.
7. Complete the design and then analyze the design.
8. Define the normalization rules.

The data analysis stage is analyzing user requirements, logical design, physical design. Logical design includes analysis needs such as DFD to know the flow and flow of data from information systems, and data dictionaries are used to store information, system design includes ERD, physical design, database design, input/output design, The input/output design is used to create the screen display and consistent form, ERD is used to determine the relationship between master data, view database design is designed to meet the information needs of a company.

C. Tourism

Sungai Pisang is a village located in the Bungus Teluk Kabung District, Padang City, West Sumatra Province. The area of Sungai Pisang Village is 9.14 km² with a population of 1,914 people and a total number of family heads (KK) as many as 314 families. Almost all heads of families have a livelihood as fishermen because of their geographical location on the outskirts of the coast.[5]

Geographical condition of Sungai Pisang Village, which is located in beachfront and not too far from the island's tourism potential which is famous in West Sumatra, is an opportunity for the Sungai Pisang community, especially the Big Dipper fisherman, to improve their standard of living. Tourism is one of the industries capable of providing sustainable economic growth fast in terms of providing employment, income, tariffs life, and in activating other sectors of production within tourist receiving country. Island tour now become a popular tourism object in West Sumatra. To Enjoying island tours requires good transportation services bring tourists from the mainland to the island in question. Island tourism transportation services are provided by the community Sungai Pisang as a livelihood other than as a fisherman in the evening. Every family head in Sungai Pisang usually have one dipper to take tourists to various island tours around the Sungai Pisang. There are 5 island tourist destination that can be used as a destination users of island hopping transportation services on the Sungai Pisang namely

Pasumpahan Island, Pamutusan Island, Pagang Island, Sirandah Island and Suwarnadwipa Island.

Apart from the conditions above, the number of tourists is also minimal also exacerbated by road conditions from the main traffic road towards the Bad Pisang River area (unpaved and many holes), so that tourists find it difficult to reach the Sungai Pisang area by using private transportation. In addition, there is no public transportation available, both in the form of village transportation and motorcycle taxis for transportation to the Sungai Pisang area. It triggers the minimum number of tourists who come to Sungai Pisang for using the island's tourist attraction transportation services from fishermen Big Dipper on the Sungai Pisang. While the road to the Bungus area there are good roads and available public transportation adequate.

The rapid development of the internet today is very affect the business world, especially in the marketing system. The development of information technology allows humans around the world to exchange information with large numbers unlimited transactions and can be accessed anytime and anywhere . The role of the internet for marketing products and services provide benefits and positive impacts for sustainability business. [5]

Online marketing of products or services aims to facilitate sales so as to reduce costs expenses such as advertising costs and the cost of making brochures. New innovations in digital business have opened up opportunities for carry out a transformation in the marketing information system that used to be offline to online. Forms of online marketing provide a great opportunity for companies to do expansion of market segmentation without limitation of space and time. Marketing activities carried out with the support of the internet, one of them is a mobile web service. Mobile web can used by a company to support activities such as presenting company information, marketing products or services, and make it easier for customers to find information about the company. The emergence of new innovations in business digital opens opportunities for transformation process changing the shape of the offline marketing information system be online. Web-based applications are widely used for improve the effectiveness and efficiency of an activity to design a product marketing information system. Therefore, it is necessary to formulate a business improvement strategy Big Dipper fisherman through marketing information system design mobile web based. A marketing information system is a structures, complex interactions between people, machines, and procedures to be able to produce an orderly flow of information, from sources inside and outside the company to be able to used in decision making accountable to the leadership. Information Systems The marketing of the island's tourism .product is based on a mobile web that isdesigned using the PHP programming language and MySQL database supported. Information system design. This marketing is expected to increase the number of tourists island tourism users as an effort to increase the fisherman's economy.

At the stage of implementing the information system marketing of the island tourism product which has been designed to be able to used by fishermen in marketing their services island tour transportation. Big Dipper fisherman is given training on the use of marketing information systems marketing Island tourism to increase the number of tourists as

an effort to increase the economy of Big Dipper fishermen. In implementation stage, the following activities are carried out[5]:

1. Moving the website from localhost to the hosting server.
2. Creation of database on hosting and application of rights user access to the database.
3. Application testing and improvement (debugging).

Furthermore, the operation of the marketing information system carried out by Big Dipper fishermen as admins who are trained to be able to operate a marketing information system with effective.[5]

IV. CONCLUSION

The design results involve four actors with the authority and different levels of access. These differences will increase information security, so that various forms of fraud involving the manipulation of data by another party can be minimized. In addition, the design of information systems also eliminating repetitive set point data input activities usually carried out by Operator 1. Eliminate the activity reduce the time required to implement the whole process, thereby increasing efficiency system. In addition, loop elimination also minimizes potential the occurrence of human errors and writing errors in the process data input. Based on this, it can be concluded that the design of information systems with web-based applications has been able to help increase efficiency and minimize the weakness of the existing information system at the PT Process IV Laboratory at this time.

The development of information technology has changed the way and our daily behavior, including changing the way we transact. Advances in information technology in business gave rise to a digital transaction model called e-commerce. One of the advantages of transacting business with e-commerce is the wide market share that can be reached. The advantages of doing business with e-commerce should be also used by SMEs in Indonesia Bangka Belitung Islands. This research found that the technological constraint factor is the most important factor affect the use of e-commerce with a weight of 33.2%. The sub-criteria of the most important information constraint criteria influencing the use of e-commerce is mastery information technology by 38.6%. Synthesis results respect to The goal shows that the typical food production business is a type of businesses that are mostly carried out by small businesses and middle school in Bangka Belitung. The results of this study can used by relevant stakeholders to increasing attention to mastery of technology information that can facilitate business transactions with e-commerce.

From this research (case study), several conclusions were obtained that is:

1. Warehousing information system implemented in CV. ABB has been quite effective in suppressing problems that occur in warehouse management so far.
2. With the warehousing management information system in CV. ABB, warehouse management becomes more accountable and transparent.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. Yuliandra and R. F. Wulan, "Perancangan Sistem Informasi Pengendalian Kualitas pada Laboratorium Proses IV PT X," *J. Optimasi Sist. Ind.*, vol. 17, no. 2, p. 113, 2018, doi: 10.25077/josi.v17.n2.p113-125.2018.
- [2] J. S. P. Tyoso, *Sistem Informasi Manajemen*. Deepublish, 2016.
- [3] H. Magdalena and S. Irawadi, "Analisis Faktor – Faktor Pendukung atau Penghambat Pelaku Bisnis UMKM di Bangka Belitung dalam Memanfaatkan E-Commerce.," *J. Optimasi Sist. Ind.*, vol. 17, no. 1, p. 16, 2018, doi: 10.25077/josi.v17.n1.p16-25.2018.
- [4] H. H. Azwir and O. Patriani, "Perbaikan Pengelolaan Pergudangan Melalui Penerapan Sistem Informasi Pergudangan di CV. ABB," *J. Optimasi Sist. Ind.*, vol. 16, no. 1, p. 10, 2017, doi: 10.25077/josi.v16.n1.p10-24.2017.
- [5] E. Amrina, I. Kamil, H. Triha, and A. A. Yulianto, "Sistem Informasi Pemasaran Biduk Wisata Pulau Berbasis Web Mobile (Studi Kasus di Sungai Pisang, Padang, Sumatera Barat)," *J. Optimasi Sist. Ind.*, vol. 18, no. 2, p. 142, 2019, doi: 10.25077/josi.v18.n2.p142-152.2019.